

Deliverable D9.2 - Communication kit

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Declaration: Any work or result described therein is a genuine output of the AtlantECO project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant.

Table of Content

1	Version History	3
2	Executive summary	4
3	Introduction	5
4	Infographics	6
4.1	Visual aspect	6
5	Presentation document	7
5.1	Visual aspect	7
5.2	Framework and content of the document	7
6	AtlantECO presentation video	12
6.1	Visual aspect	12
6.2	Framework of the video	12
6.3	Links to the video	14
7	Newsletter	15
7.1	Visual Identity	15
7.2	Newsletter framework	15
8	Annexes	17

1 Version History

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
0.1	Camille Lextray	Initial draft	07.06.2021
0.2	Eloise Trabut	Review, contributions, and formatting	14.06.2021
0.3	Camille Lextray	Final version	12.10.2021
1.0	Eloise Trabut	Review for submission	13.10.2021

2 Executive summary

The Deliverable “Communication kit” is produced as part of the Work Package 9 “Communication, capacity building and outreach” and sets out to establish the initial media for communication to present the program and give communication tools for use by partners and media stakeholders.

The tools presented in this document are made for different purposes and targets.

- Presentation document: used by partners to present the project during events, it can also be used by journalists and other media stakeholders to have an overview of AtlantECO.
- Project overview video: targeted towards the public. It will be used to present AtlantECO on digital platforms, social networks and during events.
- Public Newsletter: targets subscribed audience who are already interested in AtlantECO and used to engage with prospective audiences.

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction

The ambition of AtlantECO is to develop and apply a novel, unifying framework that provides knowledge-based resources to design policies, support decision making and engage with citizens to encourage responsible behaviour to manage the Atlantic system and protect its Ecosystem Services provision.

The aim of AtlantECO is to determine the structure and function of Atlantic microbiome in the context of ocean circulation and presence of pollutants, e.g., plastics, to assess its role in driving the dynamics of Atlantic ecosystems at basin and regional scales; its potential of being used as a sensor of ecosystem state and the mechanisms by which it drives the provision of five ES. This is key to improve our predictions on future provision of ES in the basin and to favour the establishment of a sustainable Blue Growth strategy for an All- Atlantic community.

To realise this vision, AtlantECO has four objectives which are to

- 1) Assess dynamics of Atlantic marine ecosystems, their ES provision, and the interplay of both with socio-economic activities.
- 2) Increase knowledge and data on microbiomes, plastics, the plastisphere and carbon fluxes that support ecosystems at basin scale using best practices and integrative sampling strategies, novel genomics, imaging and biogeochemical methods, bioinformatics, and modelling approaches.
- 3) Assess and predict the cumulative impacts of multiple stressors on ecosystem status and dynamics and ES provision, identifying their drivers and role on tipping points, assessing their changes in recovery of ecosystem structures, functions, and services, and developing eco-socio-economic models to predict future trajectories.
- 4) Deploy a systemic strategy to build capacity and transfer knowledge for a seamless engagement between science, industry, policy, and society. To achieve these objectives AtlantECO brings together experts and pioneers from Europe, South America, and South Africa with the relevant resources, knowledge and experience.

The conference “A New Era of Blue Enlightenment”, held in Lisbon in July 2017, presented an ambitious vision for a future integrated Atlantic scientific cooperation program, shared by the European Union, Brazil and South Africa. This vision was expressed in the Belem Statement, a High-Level political declaration signed by the European commissioner for research and innovation, the president of Portugal and ministers from Brazil and South Africa. The All-Atlantic projects are now working to deliver the objectives of the Belem Statement.

Within this framework, AtlantECO will highlight the importance of Atlantic marine ecosystems, building synergies with the “sister projects”, we will focus our communication on the microbiome, invisible multitude that drifts in the ocean, as well as on the microplastics and the microbiome which lives on them, and the concept of connectivity or how everything moves around in the ocean.

The AtlantECO communication kit presented in this document details the content of the communication media that will be deployed. These media will support the need of communication of the partners and will give multi targeted tools to ensure a fluid communication.

4 Infographics

4.1 Visual aspect

The visual identity of the infographics is based on the branding developed by AtlantECO. The infographic gives an overview of the action of the programme and explains the three scientific pillars, the four activity streams, and the Ecosystem Services targeted. All infographics are available for viewing and download on the [AtlantECO website](https://atlanteco.eu).

5 Presentation document

5.1 Visual aspect

The presentation document is illustrated with extracts from the overview infographics and the content presented in the overview video. All elements of the visual identity from the infographics will be part of the project's graphical chart and be used throughout communication material produced. The presentation document can be found on [AtlantECO website](#).

5.2 Framework and content of the document

36 PARTNERS FROM 13 COUNTRIES
 France, Belgium, Switzerland, United Kingdom, Italy, Spain, Portugal, Norway, Hungary, Netherlands, Germany, South Africa & Brazil

Content

Research field: the Atlantic Ocean 2
 The study of the Atlantic Ocean: a crucial issue for tomorrow’s challenges 3
 The AtlantECO project 4
 Objectives of the project 5
 Activity streams 6
 Scientific pillars 7
 Ecosystem services 9
 Case studies 10

Research field: the Atlantic Ocean

The Atlantic Ocean is a key component of the Earth system. With a surface of 106,5 million square kilometres, it is the second largest ocean basin on Earth. The Atlantic Ocean powers the overturning circulation, a fundamental component of the climate system. It also comprises regions of contrasting nutrient concentrations, which sustain a diversity of food webs that impact ocean productivity and fish stocks.

Biogeochemical processes drive more than 30% of the global ocean absorption of atmospheric CO₂, with a possible decrease in the incoming

decades. The Atlantic Ocean is also a pillar of the global maritime economy. Marine ecosystems are increasingly affected by climate change and other environmental threats, yet the ocean-based economy is expected to double in the next 20 years.

Marine ecosystems are largely driven by the ocean microbiome, the ensemble of microscopic organisms that inhabit the ocean, classically known as plankton, which process most of the fluxes of energy and matter, including pollutants, through the system.

The study of the Atlantic Ocean: a crucial issue for tomorrow’s challenges

The Atlantic ocean is largely unexplored and therefore unknown. In the context of rapid demographic growth and climate change, one of the greatest challenges of our times is to identify and preserve existing ecosystem services and good environmental status. Changes in temperature, ocean circulation, and the supply of essential or harmful chemical substances are among the stressors that cumulatively impact marine ecosystems and hamper their ability to provide key services.

While increased incidences of harmful algal blooms, invasive species, parasites

and jellyfish are more frequently observed, the consequences of increasing human activities on marine ecosystems and their services are still poorly quantified, especially in the South Atlantic. Consequently, there is a need to develop a framework to better understand these marine ecosystems, linking observations, numerical models, policy design, and their implementation. Furthermore, current analyses focus on specific elements of pelagic and benthic systems, oversimplifying the complexity of the system.

The AtlantECO project

AtlantECO is a Research and Innovation project which is funded under the Horizon 2020 programme.

It brings together 36 partners from 13 countries in Europe, Brazil and South Africa as well as many collaborators from around the Atlantic basin.

Throughout the project, AtlantECO will engage with a range of stakeholders from citizens to scientists, and actors from the policy and the industry sectors, in order to increase awareness, develop capacity, promote responsible behaviour and stimulate Blue Growth.

AtlantECO aims to develop knowledge-based resources to assess and forecast the sustainability of the Atlantic Ocean and its ecosystem services. These resources are based on novel observations and models describing marine microbiomes, plastics & the plastisphere, and the connectivity of ecosystems at regional, basin and global scales. Knowledge will be shared among scientists, industry, policy-makers and citizens in order to help sustain a Blue Growth strategy for an All-Atlantic community.

4 AtlantECO

Objectives of the project

AtlantECO has four objectives:

1. ECOSYSTEMS

Assess dynamics of Atlantic marine ecosystems, their ecosystem services provision and the interplay of both with socio-economic activities.

2. KNOWLEDGE

Increase data and knowledge and data on microbiomes, plastics, the plastisphere and carbon fluxes that support ecosystems at basin scale using best practices and integrative sampling strategies, novel genomics, imaging and biogeochemical methods, bioinformatics and modelling approaches.

3. IMPACTS

Assess and predict the cumulative impacts of multiple stressors on ecosystem status and dynamics and Ecosystem Services provision, identifying their drivers and role on tipping points, assessing their changes in recovery of ecosystem structures, functions and services, and developing eco-socio-economic models to predict future trajectories.

4. CAPACITY BUILDING

Deploy a systemic strategy to build capacity and transfer knowledge for a seamless engagement between science, industry, policy, and society. To achieve these objectives AtlantECO brings together experts and pioneers from Europe, South America and South Africa with the relevant resources, knowledge and experience.

AtlantECO 5

Activity streams

The ambition of AtlantECO is to develop and apply a novel, unifying framework for providing knowledge-based resources to design policies, support decision making and engage with citizens to encourage responsible behaviour to manage the Atlantic system and protect its Ecosystem Services provision.

'To realise this vision, AtlantECO will implement four Activity Streams to reach its four objectives'.

MAP THE CURRENT STATE

Map the current state of marine ecosystem composition, functioning, health and services using high quality data at global scale.

GENERATE NEW DIGITAL KNOWLEDGE

Generate new digital knowledge from scientific expeditions and citizen science, using innovative numerical models.

FORECAST CHANGES

Forecast the impacts of human and climatic pressures on complex ecosystems using eco-socio-economic models.

SHARE AND USE KNOWLEDGE

Share and use knowledge among scientists, industry, policy-makers and citizens. Make all data available via open databases.

6 AtlantECO

Scientific pillars

MICROBIOMES

The Ocean microbiomes includes all the microscopic life in the Ocean. Every litre of seawater contains billions of microorganisms, the composition and activity of this group of microorganisms indicate the health of the marine ecosystem in which they live. This invisible majority, which makes up the Ocean microbiomes, has received far less attention than large charismatic species despite its essential role for the health of the Planet:

- ▶ Marine microbiomes are responsible for half of the oxygen produced on earth every day and capture 25% of the carbon, generated by human activities.
- ▶ It regulates the temperature on earth.
- ▶ It plays a key part in nourishing ecosystems.

AtlantECO 7

PLASTICS & THE PLASTISPHERE

One of the most pressing environmental challenges is the growing amount of plastic in our oceans, it is so large that plastic is regarded as a marker of the Anthropocene. Most of this plastic quickly fragments into micro- and nano-plastics. Less than 250,000 tons of plastic is accounted for as floating on the surface of the ocean, which means that more than 99% of the plastic that ever entered the ocean is 'missing'. Microplastic is equivalent to around 0.1% of global plankton biomass and it is increasing.

A growing body of research has investigated plastic distribution and toxicity for marine fauna. Organisms can get entangled in larger pieces of plastic

or ingest smaller pieces. The plastic is transported by ocean currents and waves. Some of it passes through regions of high biodiversity where it can particularly impact marine life. Accurate maps of the transport and distribution of marine plastics are therefore crucial to assess its impact and to inform mitigation strategies, including removal.

AtlantECO will map plastic distribution in the Atlantic basin, identify or infer the putative sources, analyse the interaction between the plastics and the microbiome (e.g. aggregation, scavenging, ingestion, weathering, biofouling) and quantify their transfer 'up' in the pelagic food web and their transfer 'down', toward the deeper oceanic layers and sea floor.

SEASCAPE AND CONNECTIVITY

Seascape is the mapping of the pathway and timescales on which ocean flows transport material between different regions. It's a useful framework to characterize the interactions between physics, chemistry and biology in the ocean. Like the atmosphere, the ocean

has the equivalent of high and low pressure areas, fronts, trade winds and cyclones. The ocean is in constant motion, full of small-scale features that play a crucial role in transporting heat, nutrients, organisms, and microplastics between regions.

Case studies

To demonstrate the exploitation potential of AtlantECO knowledge towards a range of applications, five case studies have been defined in AtlantECO, the aim of the case studies is to ensure and demonstrate the applicability of methods, technologies, results and outputs for real applications.

- **CS1 MOLECULAR BIOPROSPECTING**
Discover new bioproducts & chemicals for industrial applications with high socio-economic value, for example new ways to produce pharmaceutical products or enzymes able to digest plastics.
- **CS2 IMPACT OF DRILLING IN BRAZIL AND INFLUENCING POLICIES**
Study the impact of oil and gas extraction platforms on marine microbiomes, and engage with the industry and policy makers about future regulations and practice in the gas and oil industry.
- **CS3 EARLY HAZARD DETECTION IN AQUACULTURE**
Monitor aquaculture sites using imaging and genetic sensors to detect potential harmful microorganisms.
- **CS4 ENVIRONMENTAL REGULATION OF COASTAL AREAS IN THE CONTEXT OF SHALLOW SEA DIAMOND MINING**
Study the impact of shallow diamond mining on marine microbiomes, and engage with the industry and policy makers about future regulations and practice in mining areas.
- **CS5 VALUE CHAIN FOR FOOD PRODUCTION: ADAPTING TO CLIMATE CHANGE**
Explore molecular databases from the marine microbiome; look for genetic adaptation to "salty" environments; and transfer this knowledge to industries working on the adaptation of crops (tomatoes, potatoes) in response to sea level rise and reduced precipitations.

Ecosystem services

Ecosystem service frameworks have mostly been developed and implemented in terrestrial ecosystems. Their application has lagged behind in the marine environment, mainly due to a lack of data both on the supply side of the ecosystem service framework and on the demand side (monetary and non-monetary valuation data for benefits), which has arisen partly because there is little standard methodology to collect these data in marine systems.

The project will focus on five Ecosystem Services :

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6 AtlantECO presentation video

6.1 Visual aspect

The footage used to build the video was provided by the partners. Elements of the overview infographics were animated to illustrate concepts from the project throughout the video.

6.2 Framework of the video

Part 1 : What is the Atlantic Ocean

Image :

Footage of the Atlantic Ocean shot by a drone
Footage of the biodiversity
Footage of the microbiome

Sound :

Voice over explaining what we know about the Atlantic Ocean, what has been explored, the basic facts about it

The Atlantic ocean has a surface of 106,5 million square km and is the second largest ocean basin on earth. It is a key component of the Earth system and a home to a large biodiversity. Marine ecosystems are largely driven by the ocean microbiome, the ensemble of microscopic organisms, classically known as plankton, and play a key role in the distribution of energy and matter, including pollutants, through the system. The Atlantic ocean plays a key part in the food web and is an essential component of the climate system.

Part 2 : Why is it important to study the Atlantic Ocean

Image :

Person 1 explains why our research is important.

Sound :

The Atlantic ocean is largely unexplored and therefore unknown. In the context of rapid population growth and climate change, one of the greatest challenges of our times is to identify and preserve existing Ecosystem Services and Good Environmental Status. Changes in temperature, ocean circulation, overfishing, and the amount of essential or harmful chemical substances are among the stressors that cumulatively impact marine ecosystems and hamper their ability to provide key services.

Part 3 The AtlantECO program

Image :

Illustration with key numbers and key facts about the program
13 countries : special highlight the collaboration Europe - Brazil and South Africa
36 partners
3 years
x expeditions

Sound :

Person 1 explains
AtlantECO is a scientific project funded by the European Union.

The ambition of AtlantECO is to develop a better understanding and management of the Atlantic Ocean ensuring it can reliably provide its ecosystem services.

AtlantECO will engage with citizens and actors from the industry and policy sectors in order to stimulate responsible behaviour and Blue Growth.

The project focuses on three pillars of research: plastic and the plastisphere, seascape connectivity and microbiomes.

Part 4 : The three scientific pillars

Image :

Image of the interviews then animations illustrating what the voice over is explaining

Sound :

Plastic: Person 2 presents the first scientific pillar

One of the most pressing current environmental challenges is the growing amount of plastic in our oceans. Most of this plastic quickly fragments into micro- and nano-plastics. 99% of the plastic that ever entered the ocean is 'missing'. On the other hand, microplastic is equivalent to around 0.1% of global plankton biomass.

AtlantECO will map the plastic distribution in the Atlantic basin, identify or infer the putative sources, analyse the interaction between the plastics and the microbiome and quantify their transfer 'up' in the pelagic food web and their transfer 'down', toward the deeper oceanic layers and sea floor.

Seascape Person 3 presents the second scientific pillar

Seascape is the mapping of the pathway and timescales on which ocean flows transport material between different regions. To date the Atlantic seascape has been insufficiently characterized. There are many knowledge gaps on the role of key components of the seascape in determining the dispersal of tracers and the connectivity between sources and sinks. We are also missing a description of two-dimensional connectivity at the Atlantic scale to be operationally used for ecosystem services management and policy development to design spatial planning for the Atlantic. Climate change is going to impact the seascape dynamics in many, often subtle ways by, among others, enhancing superposition in layers and changing circulation patterns.

Microbiome : Person 4 presents the third scientific pillar

With AtlantECO we are embarking on the next great exploration of the seas: discovering the functioning of the ocean microbiome.

Depending on where you cast down your bucket, a typical litre of seawater is home to billions of microbes, mostly made up of no more than a single cell. Yet this multitude, which makes up the ocean microbiome, has received far less attention than charismatic species, despite their essential roles in nourishing ecosystems, and therefore humans, producing oxygen, and transporting carbon to the deep ocean. The microbiome is highly sensitive to temperature change, ocean acidification, and pollution.

Microbes are the most common creatures on the planet. Understanding the microbiome not only encompasses identifying who is present but also understanding where do they live, what can they do, and what do they do. Yet, measurements of their quantity and feeding, and of the surrounding environment remain grand challenges for humankind.

Voice over narrates:

Part 5 : Interactive map showing the expeditions

6.3 Links to the video

The video is made available on the [AtlantECO website](#) and on the [AtlantECO YouTube channel](#).

Direct links to the video are provided below

- Video in English, without subtitles: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Fi48sG8_5JA&t=50s
- Video in English, with English subtitles: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9fnWnKMYAIQ&t=113s>
- Video in English, with French subtitles: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OC42JgGXrb8&t=51s>
- Video in English, with Italian subtitles: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t0OjeyFY0W8&t=1s>
- Video in English, with Portuguese subtitles: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Fi48sG8_5JA&t=52s

7 Newsletter

7.1 Visual Identity

The visual identity of the Newsletter is declined from the graphical. The top banner presents AtlantECO's logo, and the bottom banner links to all AtlantECO's social media channels.

7.2 Newsletter framework

The following items are included on the Newsletter:

- General update (in 5 bullet points)
- Highlight of 2 to 4 articles on the website
- Photo of the month (with a sentence to give context)
- Learn more about science: Present a definition of a term linked to the AtlantECO project and present a scientific tool
- Upcoming events
- Media coverage

All Newsletter issues will be available from the AtlantECO website ([see archive](#)). The visual extract of the first issue is presented below

Search Home

View all news and stories

AtlantECO
Atlantic Ocean Research Training & Education

WORLD'S FIRST OCEANIC COORDINATOR OF ATLANTECO

World's first oceanic coordinator of AtlantECO

Top news

AtlantECO is a refresh
Despite the challenges that it has faced in the past few years, AtlantECO is now in a better position than ever to continue its mission of providing training and education to the next generation of ocean scientists.

AtlantECO's first expeditions : sets arrived in Brazil
The first of the Atlantic Oceanic Expeditions (AOE) has arrived in Brazil. The expedition is led by Dr. [Name] and will be the first of a series of expeditions that will be carried out over the next few years.

Observing Ocean sound
Observing ocean sound is a key component of the AtlantECO program. This is because sound is a key indicator of ocean health and can be used to monitor changes in the environment.

Meet the team

UFSCAR
The National Oceanic Coordinator of AtlantECO is Dr. [Name]. He is a leading expert in oceanography and has been instrumental in the development of the AtlantECO program.

NIOZ
The National Oceanic Coordinator of AtlantECO is Dr. [Name]. He is a leading expert in oceanography and has been instrumental in the development of the AtlantECO program.

AtlantECO in the media

Science Advances
Environmental vulnerability of the global ocean epipelagic plankton community interaction

Calendar & events

It's a big day in Bahia
The first day of the AtlantECO program is a big day in Bahia. The program is a key component of the AtlantECO program and will be the first of a series of events that will be carried out over the next few years.

Science corner

AtlantECO in numbers

AtlantECO is composed of 1000+ partners, universities, researchers, and students from 100+ countries.

AtlantECO partners are from 100+ different countries, in Europe, Latin America, Africa and Asia.

AtlantECO program is open to all.

AtlantECO program is open to all.

AtlantECO is a global program that is open to all. It is a key component of the AtlantECO program and will be the first of a series of events that will be carried out over the next few years.

8 Annexes

7.1 Branding

The support all communication activities, AtlantECO has developed its branding early on in the project. This is used on all material and platforms to ensure that the project image is identifiable by all over time.

7.1.1 Logos

The AtlantECO logo has been declined in multiple formats to allow an array of use and media support. Its main elements are the project acronym, the project title, and a set of six critters. The background for each version is either transparent, white, dark blue or dark grey. Below are some examples of the logo in different formats.

7.1.1.1 Full official logo

7.1.1.2 Acronym and critters-long

7.1.1.3 Acronym and critters- square

7.1.1.4 Critters only

7.1.2 Colour palette

The following colours are used in AtlantECO branding

	HEX: #575756	R: 87; G: 87; B: 86
	HEX: #174571	R: 23; G: 69; B: 113
	HEX: #136EB9	R: 19; G: 110; B: 185
	HEX: #3192F0	R: 49; G: 146; B: 240
	HEX: #35A8E0	R: 53; G: 168; B: 224
	HEX: #46BC1E	R: 70; G: 188; B: 30
	HEX: #F5A733	R: 245; G: 167; B: 51
	HEX: #E5007E	R: 229; G: 0; B: 126
	HEX: #BF7590	R: 191; G: 117; B: 114

Figure 3 AtlantECO branding- colour palette

7.1.3 Font

The AtlantECO font is “Overlock Regular 400” available for [download on Google fonts](#).